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POSSIBLE CHANGES IN THE ORAL HEALTH OF PEOPLE WITH DOWN SYNDROME: INTEGRATIVE LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Oral problems may involve not only physical health, but also economic aspects and social and psychological well-being. They can even affect self-esteem, demonstrating the importance of maintaining oral health in quality of life Method: integrative literature review based on the following guiding question: what are the possible changes in the oral health of people with Down Syndrome (DS). A consultation was carried out in the LILACS and MEDLINE databases, with the descriptors in Portuguese, “oral health” and “down syndrome” and in English adopted “oral health” and “down syndrome”. Articles published in the last five years (2016 to 2021) in Portuguese, English and Spanish and freely available in full were included in the study. Results: 7 articles were included that met the defined inclusion/exclusion criteria, 4 in LILACS and 3 in MEDLINE. Conclusion: it is necessary to carry out studies with better research designs and with adults and/or elderly people with DS, since most of the selected studies focused their research on children and/or adolescents with DS.

Keywords: Dentistry. Oral Health. Down's syndrome.